

EFFECT OF LIGHT AND AGEING ON COLLOIDAL SOLUTIONS OF FERRIC HYDROXIDE AND THORIUM HYDROXIDE.

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Cataphoretic speed, conductivity and stability of colloidal solutions of ferric hydroxide and thorium hydroxide containing different amounts of impurities as brought about by dialysis are found to decrease slowly on exposure to sunlight and on ageing.

In previous papers (Desai and Barve, *Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1939, 2, 39; Vora, Barve and Desai, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1941, 13, 100; *J. Bombay Univ.*, 1941, 10, iii, 40) results of light and ageing on cataphoretic speed, conductivity and stability of colloidal solutions of arsenious sulphide, Prussian blue, gold, vanadium pentoxide, zinc ferrocyanide and ceric hydroxide containing varying amounts of impurities, as brought about by dialysis, have been given. In the present paper similar results obtained with colloidal solutions of ferric hydroxide and thorium hydroxide, whose other properties have already been exhaustively studied in this laboratory, have been presented.

Colloidal solutions of ferric hydroxide (Desai and Borkar, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1933, 29, 1269) and thorium hydroxide (Desai and Desai, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, 30, 265) were prepared as before and the various experiments performed in the same manner as in the case of colloidal zinc ferrocyanide (Vora, Barve and Desai, *loc. cit.*). All the experiments were carried out at a temperature of 30°. For both the colloidal solutions two samples have been tried (one dialysed for a short period and the other for a long period *i.e.*, before and after the maximum in the cataphoretic speed-dialysis curve is reached, Desai and Barve, *loc. cit.*) in order to note if the amount of impurity in the sol has any effect on the action of light or ageing.

The results are given in Tables I to IV. In all the tables the cataphoretic speed (cat. speed) (mean of direct and reverse movements) is corrected for viscosity and expressed in cm. sec./volt/cm. The stability results (flocculation values—F.V.) are expressed in millimoles of the electrolyte per litre of the mixture (colloid + electrolyte + water).

TABLE I.

Colloidal ferric hydroxide exposed to sunlight.

Exposure.	Sol dialysed for 4 days.			Sol dialysed for 20 days.		
	Cat. speed.	Sp. condy.	F.V. with KCl.	Cat. speed.	Sp. condy.	F.V. with KCl.
0 hr.	37.5×10^{-3}	5363×10^{-6}	5.10	51.8×10^{-3}	1436×10^{-6}	1.40
2	34.7	5318	5.00	49.6	1396	1.36
4	32.4	5270	4.86	47.6	1361	1.31
6	30.8	5217	4.68	45.8	1333	1.25

TABLE II.

Colloidal thorium hydroxide exposed to sunlight.

Exposure	Sol dialysed for 4 days.			Sol dialysed for 20 days.		
	Cat. speed.	Sp. condy.	F.V. with KCl.	Cat. speed.	Sp. condy.	F.V. with KCl.
0 hr.	36.8×10^{-3}	5047×10^{-6}	4.70	35.4×10^{-3}	824×10^{-6}	1.80
2	33.7	5025	4.52	32.3	780	1.72
4	31.8	5011	4.38	30.3	750	1.67
6	29.9	4982	4.15	28.8	726	1.58

TABLE III.

Colloidal ferric hydroxide-effect of ageing.

Age.	Sol dialysed for 12 days.			Sol dialysed for 20 days.		
	Cat. speed.	Sp. condy.	F.V. with KCl.	Cat. speed.	Sp. condy.	F.V. with KCl.
0 days.	67.2×10^{-3}	3714×10^{-6}	3.31	51.8×10^{-3}	1436×10^{-6}	1.40
31	66.5	3692	3.25	51.4	1412	1.34
61	65.4	3648	3.21	51.2	1369	1.31

TABLE IV.

Colloidal thorium hydroxide-effect of ageing.

Age.	Sol dialysed for 12 days.			Sol dialysed for 20 days.		
	Cat. speed.	Sp. condy.	F.V. with KCl.	Cat. speed.	Sp. condy.	F.V. with KCl.
0 days.	44.3×10^{-3}	2317×10^{-6}	3.20	35.4×10^{-3}	824×10^{-6}	1.80
31	43.5	2258	3.15	34.2	794	1.77
61	42.1	2177	3.11	33.4	767	1.72

DISCUSSION.

Exposure to Sunlight.—It will appear from the results in Tables I and II that in both cases the cataphoretic speed, conductivity and stability decrease slowly on exposure to sunlight for short period as well as long-period dialysed colloidal solutions. These results are similar to those obtained with colloidal solutions of vanadium pentoxide and can be explained in the same manner (Desai and Barve, *loc. cit.*).

Effect of Ageing.—As in the case of exposure to sunlight, the cataphoric speed, conductivity and stability decrease continuously on ageing (Tables III and IV) of both the short-period and long-period dialysed colloidal solutions of ferric hydroxide and thorium hydroxide. The results can be explained in the same manner as those obtained for vanadium pentoxide (Desai and Barve, *loc. cit.*).

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